

Exploring the Versatility of Membrane-Free Battery Concept Using Different Combinations of Immiscible Redox Electrolytes

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Supporting Information

ABSTRACT: Lately, the field of redox flow batteries is flourishing because of the emergence of new redox chemistries, including organic compounds, new electrolytes, and innovative designs. Recently, we reported an original membrane-free battery concept based on the mutual immiscibility of an aqueous catholyte containing hydroquinone and an ionic liquid anolyte containing *para*-benzoquinone as redox species. Here, we investigate the versatility of this concept exploring the electrochemical performance of 10 redox electrolytes based on different solvents, such as propylene carbonate, 2-butanone, or neutral-pH media, and containing different redox organic molecules, such as 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl, 4-hydroxy-

2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl (OH-TEMPO), or substituted anthraquinones. The most representative electrolytes were paired and used as immiscible anolyte–catholyte in 5 different membrane-free batteries. Those batteries with substituted anthraquinones in the anolyte exhibited up to 50% improved open-circuit voltage (2.1 V), an operating voltage of 1.75 V, and 62% higher power density compared with our previous work. On the other hand, the partition coefficient of redox molecules between the two immiscible phases and the inherent self-discharge occurring at the interphase are revealed as intrinsic features affecting the performance of this type of membrane-free battery. It was successfully demonstrated that the functionalization of redox molecules is an interesting strategy to tune the partition coefficients mitigating the crossover that provokes low battery efficiency. As a result, the cycling life of a battery having OH-TEMPO as active species in the catholyte and containing propylene carbonate-based anolyte was evaluated over 300 cycles, achieving 85% capacity retention. These results demonstrated the huge versatility and countless possibilities of this new membrane-free battery concept.

KEYWORDS: redox flow battery, membrane-free battery, organic redox flow battery, organic redox compound, immiscible electrolytes

INTRODUCTION

Redox flow batteries (RFBs) have been recognized as a viable technology for applications such as peak shifting and grid stabilization because their energy and power densities are totally decoupled.¹ As a matter of fact, this is their main differentiating feature from the solid-state batteries and one of their most important advantages. However, conventional vanadium RFBs exhibit low energy density, which is an important limitation for their widespread implementation. Other limitations are the toxicity, scarcity, and high price of vanadium species and the high price and poor performance of ion-exchange membranes.^{2,3}

In the last years, organic redox molecules, including quinones,^{4–6} phenothiazines,⁷ viologens,⁸ nitroxides,^{8–10} pyridines,^{11,12} methoxybenzene,^{13,14} quinoxaline,¹⁵ and phthalimide derivatives,¹⁶ have been identified as good candidates to

substitute metallic compounds in a new category of RFB, the so-called organic RFBs (ORFBs).^{2,17–25} The growing interest of the scientific community in this topic is triggered by some particularities of these organic molecules:^{19,20,26} (i) most of them are nontoxic, eco-friendly, and sustainable; (ii) their electrochemical and physicochemical properties, such as redox potential or solubility, can be tuned via chemical modification;^{6,27} (iii) some of them undergo multiple electron transfer, which will result in higher charge storage capacity;^{11,28,29} and (iv) they are naturally abundant and thus their cost and availability is less constrained by the production and reserves of key elements.³⁰

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Table 1. Different Combinations of Immiscible Anolyte and Catholyte and Theoretical OCV of the Corresponding Membrane-Free Batteries^a

Battery	Anolyte (-)		Catholyte (+)		OCV	Main changes/ Main innovation
	Electrolyte media	Redox Compound	Electrolyte media	Redox Compound		
Previous Work ³⁶	PYR ₁₄ TFSI	 H ₂ Q	1.4	Proof- of concept		
A	=	 2,3DMAQ	=	=	1.95	Different redox organic molecule in the anolyte/ Higher battery voltage and power density
B	=	 Oilblue N	=	=	2.1	
C	2-Butanone (0.1 M TBAPF ₆)	=	=	=	1.1	Common and cheaper solvent in the anolyte/ Less-expensive battery
D	PC (0.1 M TBAPF ₆)	=	=	=	1.0	
E	=	=	0.1 M NaCl (aq)	 TEMPO	1.5	Different redox organic molecule and neutral media/ Higher battery voltage and less-corrosive catholyte
F	PC +PYR ₁₄ TFSI (75+25 %w)	=	0.5 M NaCl(aq)	 OH-TEMPO	1.0	Cheaper anolyte and more soluble redox compound in the neutral catholyte/ less-corrosive and more concentrated catholyte, less-expensive battery
G	=	 OH-TEMPO	2.05	Different redox organic molecules in both catholyte and anolyte, neutral catholyte/ Higher battery		

Table 1. continued

Battery	Anolyte (-)		Catholyte (+)		OCV	Main changes/ Main innovation
	Electrolyte media	Redox Compound	Electrolyte media	Redox Compound		
H	=	 OH- TEMPO	2.2	voltage and less-corrosive catholyte		
I	2-Butanone (0.1 M TBAPF ₆)	=	0.5 M NaCl (aq)	 OH- TEMPO	1.2	Common and cheaper solvent in the anolyte and neutral media in the catholyte. Different redox-organic molecule in the catholyte / Less-expensive battery Less-corrosive catholyte
J	PC (0.1 M TBAPF ₆)	=	0.5 M NaCl (aq)	 OH- TEMPO	1.45	

^a(=) Same composition as that in the first example of membrane-free battery.³⁶ Theoretical OCV calculated as the difference between the redox potentials of catholyte and anolyte.

Transitioning to nonaqueous electrolytes in RFB is attracting a huge interest because it will eliminate the redox-potential restrictions caused by water electrolysis endowing higher battery voltage and energy density and increasing choices of suitable redox materials, including multi-electron-transfer reactions.³¹ In spite of this growing interest, the development of nonaqueous RFBs is still in its infancy and important challenges such as poor efficiencies, huge internal resistance, limited solubility of the active materials, and poor cyclability remain to be addressed.^{23,32}

Regardless of the electrolyte nature, except polymer-based RFBs,^{9,33} where crossover can be mitigated with an inexpensive size-exclusion separator, most RFBs require an ion-exchange membrane to prevent the crossover of active species. This key element can account for more than 30% of the cost of the battery³⁴ and may limit the long-term battery performance because of unavoidable cross-contamination and insufficient mechanical, chemical, and electrochemical stability. In addition, employing such membranes in nonaqueous RFBs results in huge internal resistance of the battery.³⁵ This along with the low intrinsic conductivity of these electrolytes leads to batteries with poor voltage efficiency and power densities 2 or 3 orders of magnitude lower than that of aqueous RFBs.³⁵

As a practical strategy to avoid the use of membrane, we have recently demonstrated an innovative battery concept based on the immiscibility of the two redox electrolytes, in which no ion-exchange membrane or separator was used.^{36,37} Unlike other membraneless configurations, such as single-flow batteries with one of the active materials being a solid (Li, Zn, etc.) or a gas (bromine),^{38–40} or laminar flow batteries^{41,42} that rely on diffusion to separate reactants, in this proof-of-concept battery, both active species are dissolved in liquid electrolytes and are not constrained to laminar regime. Therefore, the energy and power density might be totally decoupled, and they are not limited to microfluidic designs with low power output.

In the proof-of-concept battery,^{36,37} the biphasic system was formed by an aqueous catholyte and an immiscible ionic liquid

anolyte, both containing quinone redox molecules. After immersion of two carbon felt current collectors (one in each phase), the system behaved as a battery exhibiting a discharge voltage of 0.9 V and a power density of 1.85 mW cm⁻². We anticipated that this membrane-free battery concept may be implemented to other immiscible systems (aqueous or nonaqueous solvents) and to different redox compounds, including metallic or inorganic species, as recently reported.^{43,44}

Here, we demonstrate the versatility of this membrane-free battery concept implementing different pairs of aqueous–nonaqueous immiscible redox electrolytes (indispensable condition in this battery concept), including neutral-pH aqueous electrolytes and common organic solvents, such as propylene carbonate (PC) and 2-butanone. We also employed different organic redox molecules, such as 2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl (TEMPO), 4-hydroxy-2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine-1-oxyl (OH-TEMPO), and substituted anthraquinones for catholyte and anolyte, respectively. Finally, we assembled membrane-free batteries, investigated their electrochemical response, and provided new insights into inherent aspects, such as partition coefficients demonstrating the versatility and unique character of this membrane-free battery concept.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

In order to explore the versatility of the membrane-free battery concept illustrated in Figure 1a, we have investigated the electrochemical properties of a variety of immiscible redox electrolytes. In a further step, based on their mutual immiscibility and redox potentials, different pairs of immiscible redox electrolytes were assembled together and tested in a full battery arrangement. With the double aim of increasing the voltage of the battery and demonstrating the validity of the concept with asymmetric chemistries, we have tested other redox compounds besides hydroquinone (HQ) and *para*-benzoquinone (pBQ) used in the proof-of-concept battery.³⁶ In particular, here we have investigated TEMPO, OH-

TEMPO, 2,3-dimethylantraquinone (2,3-DMAQ), and 1,4-bis(pentylamino)anthraquinone (OilBlue N) as redox-active species. Regarding the electrolyte, neutral-pH aqueous solutions and common organic solvents, such as 2-butanone and PC, were employed to replace the *N*-butyl-*N*-methylpyrrolidinium bis(trifluoromethanesulfonyl)imide (PYR₁₄TFSI) anolyte and the acidic catholyte present in the preceding battery.³⁶ Table 1 shows the composition of the different electrolytes and all possible combinations to assemble membrane-free batteries. The first example of membrane-free battery reported by our group was also included to easily identify the main compositional changes adopted in the proposed electrolytes and the presumable innovation of the batteries.

Electrochemical Characterization of Immiscible Electrolytes. The electrochemical behavior of each electrolyte was studied individually by cyclic voltammetry (CV) in 3-electrode cells and is represented in Figures 1 and S1. The theoretical open-circuit voltage (OCV) of batteries composed by pairs of immiscible anolyte–catholyte was calculated as the difference between their redox potentials (see Table 1).

It is well known that increasing the number of aromatic rings in quinoyl-based molecules and the functionalization with electron-donating groups, such as $-\text{CH}_3$, favors the delocalization of electrons, resulting in more negative redox potentials. Therefore, with the final goal of increasing the OCV of the battery, the pBQ employed in the PYR₁₄TFSI anolyte of the proof-of-concept battery was replaced by anthraquinone derivatives: 2,3-DMAQ in battery A and OilBlue N in battery B (Figure 1c,d, respectively). The catholyte of these two batteries was composed of hydroquinone (H₂Q) in acidic media, as in the proof-of-concept battery.³⁶ The CV of H₂Q in blue in Figure 1 shows that at this acidic pH the redox reaction of the H₂Q involves two electrons and two protons (see Supporting Information Scheme S1a) exchanged in only one step at 0.6 V versus NHE.^{45,46} In Figure 1b–d, it is observed that, in this aprotic PYR₁₄TFSI electrolyte, quinone compounds (Q) undergo two consecutive reversible reduction reactions to radical anion (Q^{•−}) and dianion (Q^{2−}), exchanging 2 electrons in total (see Supporting Information Scheme S1b,c).⁴⁷ As expected, the theoretical OCV of batteries A and B increased 40–50% with respect to our previous example,³⁶ reaching values as high as 1.95 and 2.1 V, respectively.

Batteries C and D (Figure 1e,f) use the same redox species as in the proof-of-concept battery, but the ionic liquid of the anolyte was changed by 2-butanone and PC, respectively. The use of these inexpensive solvents would reduce the battery cost, which is an important current goal for RFB technology. In battery C, only a pair of peaks with higher anodic peak current is observed at -0.5 V (vs NHE), which is attributable to the first step of the pBQ reaction (green curve). The second step does not occur, likely because of a degradation reaction between the radical anion (BQ^{•−}) and the electrolyte.

On the other hand, in battery D, the two steps of pBQ reaction are observed, but neither of them is reversible because the anodic peak currents are lower than the cathodic ones. This is probably because of the comproportionation reaction between the pBQ and the dianion, which compromises the reversibility of the reaction (see Supporting Information Scheme S2).^{50,51} Difficulties in stabilizing the charge of single-ring molecules such as pBQ have been observed by other groups.^{52–54}

Figure 1. (a) Schematic illustration of membrane-free battery based on immiscible electrolytes. (b–h) CVs of pairs of immiscible anolyte and catholyte (pBQ in green, H₂Q in blue, 2,3-DMAQ in pink, OilBlue N in purple, TEMPO in red, OH-TEMPO in orange). The composition of electrolytes is 20 mM of redox-active specie. Scan rate: 10 mV s^{−1}.

Battery E is composed of the same anolyte as the proof-of-concept battery, but the acidic catholyte was substituted by TEMPO dissolved in neutral-pH electrolyte. It should be noted that besides the safety advantages, neutral pH prevents undesired reactions, such as comproportionation or disproportionation of TEMPO-based molecules in acidic media.^{48,49} The CV of catholyte in Figure 1g (red curve) shows that TEMPO undergoes a reversible redox reaction at 0.75 V versus NHE, turning into its oxoammonium cation during oxidation (see Supporting Information Scheme S3). Therefore, a gain of 100 mV (OCV 1.5 V) is expected for this battery compared with the proof-of-concept one.

In an attempt to improve the reversibility of pBQ in PC, the supporting salt (TBAPF₆) used in battery D was substituted by PYR₁₄TFSI in battery F. Thus, the anolyte in battery F was composed of a mixture of PYR₁₄TFSI and PC (25–75% wt, equivalent to 0.7 M of PYR₁₄TFSI). As can be seen in Figure 1h, the large ions of PYR₁₄TFSI favor the stabilization of the BQ^{•−}, making the first step reaction more reversible (similar anodic and cathodic peak currents). However, the distorted second peak of the CV indicates that the comproportionation reaction is still taking place. It should be noted that in battery

F, the active species in the catholyte is OH-TEMPO. This functionalized TEMPO presents similar redox activity as non-functionalized TEMPO (redox potential at 0.75 V vs NHE) but higher solubility in aqueous media. In the next section we will demonstrate that this minimizes the spontaneous crossover of the OH-TEMPO from catholyte to anolyte during battery operation. Batteries G–J (Figure S1) are similar to batteries A, B, C, and D but with OH-TEMPO-based catholyte instead of H₂Q-based catholyte. Therefore, the OCV in those batteries are slightly higher because of the small shift toward more positive potentials of OH-TEMPO.

Rotating-disk electrode (RDE) experiments were performed to determine the diffusion coefficients (D) and the kinetic constants (K^0) in all electrolytes (see Supporting Information Figure S2 and Table S1). Among the formulated anolytes, OilBlue N and 2,3-DMAQ in PYR₁₄TFSI present the lower diffusion coefficients likely motivated by the high viscosity (84.33 cP) and low conductivity (2.2 mS cm⁻¹)⁵⁵ of the ionic liquid and the high size of anthraquinones in comparison with pBQ. Among the studied catholytes, the one based on H₂Q in acidic media exhibits higher D and K^0 than those based on TEMPO and OH-TEMPO in neutral-pH media. It is worth remarking that the obtained D and K^0 values are comparable to similar redox compounds employed in ORFB.^{56–58} Because the electrolytes demonstrated fast electrode kinetics, the losses because of activation polarization are expected to be not very relevant in the battery arrangement.

Electrochemical Performance of Membrane-Free Batteries. Considering the electrochemical performance of the electrolytes, the most representative pairs of immiscible electrolytes were selected and batteries A, B, D, E, and F were assembled and characterized as full membrane-free batteries. The batteries were assembled by mixing the same volume of redox electrolytes forming a biphasic system, which obviates the need of any physical separator (see Figure S3 in the Supporting Information). The electric connection was done by introducing a carbon felt electrode in each phase. It should be noted that all the experiments were carried out in non-flowing conditions, allowing a more simplified analysis of the performance of the batteries without considering the fluid-dynamics, thus reducing the number of variables and facilitating the comparison of different electrolytes. All the batteries are in a fully discharged state when assembled, so, first, the batteries were galvanostatically charged up to a certain state of charge (SOC). The electrochemical performance of each battery is detailed below.

Battery A and Battery B. Figure 2a shows the voltage of battery A and the individual potential profiles of the electrolytes during charge–discharge. The voltage of the battery exhibits a clear plateau at 1.4 V during the charging process and a stable discharge plateau at 1.35 V. This high operating voltage represents an increase of 50% compared to our previous work,³⁶ which is attributed to the more negative redox potential of 2,3-DMAQ compared with pBQ. The difference between the theoretical OCV (1.95 V) and the operating voltage indicates that the second step of the 2,3-DMAQ reaction was not reached at this SOC, as evidenced by the flat profile of the anolyte at –1.0 V. In fact, considering only the first step reaction and according to Figure 1c, the theoretical OCV is 1.58 V, which is very close to the observed operating voltage. The low overpotential at the interface (~100 mV) and the good reversibility of the two redox reactions contribute to obtaining very high Coulombic

Figure 2. Performance of battery A (SOC 35%). Active species concentration: 20 mM in catholyte and anolyte. (a) Galvanostatic charge–discharge cycle at 0.16 mA cm⁻². (b) Discharge voltage profiles of the battery at different current densities. (c) Discharge individual voltage profiles of each electrolyte and the interface at different current densities. (d) Polarization test during discharge.

efficiency (99.9%), voltage efficiency (>90%), and energy efficiency (90%). Figure 2b shows that, similar to any type of battery, increasing the current density causes a decrease in the discharge voltage because of diffusion limitations. This increasing overpotential of the battery can be attributed to the higher Ohmic polarization exhibited by the anolyte at higher currents, whereas the potential of the catholyte remains constant (Figure 2c). This might be attributed to the higher viscosity and lower conductivity of the ionic liquid anolyte and to the lower diffusion coefficient of 2,3-DMAQ compared to that of H₂Q in the catholyte. As a matter of fact, protons from aqueous catholyte are probably the ions that act as charge carriers during battery operation because their mobility is significantly higher than that of the rest of the ions involved in the system, as occurs in the proof-of-concept battery.

Regardless, the voltage–current response of the battery during the discharge shows that the voltage remains above 1 V after increasing the current up to 2.3 mA cm⁻² with no noticeable kinetics or significant mass transport limitations (Figures 2d and S4a). Similar behavior was observed during polarization in charge (Figure S4b,c). A power density value about 3 mW cm⁻² can be achieved with battery A, which is quite promising in comparison with other values for non-aqueous ORFB reported in the literature^{7,16,59} and about 62% higher than in the original battery.^{36,37} This improvement is attributable to the higher operating voltage achieved by changing the pBQ by 2,3-DMAQ. Figure S4d shows the performance evolution over cycles. The value of Coulombic efficiency, lower than 100%, can be explained by the self-discharge process occurring at the interphase. This phenomenon is associated with the direct chemical reaction between the generated species that exchange one electron at the interface turning into the original compound.⁶⁰ It is important to mention that this side reaction, also observed in microfluidic membraneless systems, is an inherent phenomenon to the membrane-free battery concept that results in values of Coulombic efficiency lower than 100%. This inherent phenomenon, which is currently being investigated in our group, can be minimized by further optimization of the cell

design and adjusting the flowing conditions to minimize the residence time of the electrolytes inside the cell.

Figure 3a shows the discharge voltage profiles of battery B, in which pBQ was substituted by OilBlue N in the $\text{PYR}_{14}\text{TFSI}$

Figure 3. Performance of battery B (SOC 35%). Active species concentration: 20 mM in catholyte and anolyte. (a) Discharge curves at different current densities. (b) Discharge polarization test.

anolyte, keeping the same catholyte. The behavior of battery B is similar to that revealed by battery A. As shown in Figure 3a, the large theoretical OCV of 2.1 V (calculated from CV in Figure 1d) leads to a battery operating voltage of 1.75 V, which is one of the highest voltages reported for nonaqueous ORFB.^{7,16,57,61} Similar to battery A, the physicochemical properties of the anolyte causes higher Ohmic polarizations in its potential profile (Figure S5a) and the self-discharge phenomenon is also visible (Figure S5d). The results obtained in the polarization tests corroborate this performance (Figures 3b and S5b,c). Despite the lower D and K^0 of OilBlue N compared to pBQ, battery B delivered 35% higher power density (2.5 mW cm^{-2}) than the proof-of-concept battery^{36,37} likely because of the double operating voltage attained for this battery.

In Figure S6, the CVs of immiscible electrolytes and discharge profiles of battery A and B are represented together with the proof-of-concept battery for easier analysis. The improvement in the theoretical OCV, the operating voltage, as well as the power density achieved in batteries A and B in comparison with our previous results³⁶ is because of the different active species use in the anolyte.

Battery D. In an attempt to expand the application of membrane-free battery concept to conventional solvents, the $\text{PYR}_{14}\text{TFSI}$ ionic liquid used as anolyte in the proof-of-concept battery³⁶ was replaced by PC in battery D. According to the CV studies, the theoretical OCV of battery D is 1.00 V (see Figure 1f). As it was mentioned before, the parasitic reaction of comproportionation among the pBQ and its dianion takes place in PC media, so the potential of the anolyte was limited at -0.5 V during charge to hinder the formation of the dianion. Figure 4a shows that during the charge, both catholyte and anolyte exhibit quite stable potentials at 0.42 and -0.4 V , respectively. As a consequence, the battery voltage is stable at around 0.6 V. Throughout the discharge, the potential of the catholyte continues completely flat at 0.4 V, whereas the potential of the anolyte slowly decreases, leading to a slow decrease in the battery potential at about 0.55 V. Profound discharge experiments at different current densities (Figures 4b and S7a) demonstrated that the performance of the battery is influenced mostly by the anolyte that is less conductive and more viscous (2.50 cP) than the aqueous catholyte. In addition, because of the different ion mobility, protons from the catholyte are likely the charge carriers during the battery operation. Moreover, the D and K^0 exhibited by pBQ in PC are

Figure 4. Performance of battery D (SOC 25%). Active species concentration: 20 mM in catholyte and anolyte. (a) Galvanostatic charge–discharge cycle at 0.16 mA cm^{-2} . (b) Discharge voltage profiles of the battery at different current densities.

lower than that revealed by H_2Q in the aqueous media, affecting the battery performance (see Table S1). The potential–current response of the battery during discharge (Figure S7b) is also controlled by high Ohmic polarization revealed by the anolyte (see Figure S7c). It is worth remarking that the battery failure at the end of the discharge is because of the sudden drop in anolyte potential. This high concentration polarization might be attributed to the poor redox reversibility of pBQ in PC evidenced by the CV. In Figure 1f the CV shows that the anodic peak current was much larger than the cathodic one, meaning that only some of the reduced species during charge were able to be re-oxidized during discharge. This poor reversibility of pBQ in PC is reflected in the long-term battery performance that loses about 40% of initial capacity in less than 15 cycles (see Figure S7d).

Battery E. The effect of replacing the active species in the catholyte was explored in this battery. Here, the acidic catholyte containing H_2Q utilized in our proof-of-concept battery³⁶ was replaced by neutral solution of TEMPO, whereas the same anolyte was used (pBQ in $\text{PYR}_{14}\text{TFSI}$). According to Figure 1g, the theoretical OCV of this battery will increase 100 mV with respect to the proof-of-concept battery reaching up to 1.5 V. Figure 5a shows that during charge, the voltage profile of battery E exhibits two plateaus at about 1.0 and 1.4 V corresponding to the two reduction steps of pBQ in the

Figure 5. Performance of battery E (SOC 35%). Active species concentration: 40 mM in catholyte and 20 mM in anolyte. (a) Galvanostatic charge–discharge cycle at 0.08 mA cm^{-2} . (b) Discharge voltage profiles of the battery at different current densities. (c) Discharge individual voltage profiles of each electrolyte and the interface at different current densities. (d) Polarization test during discharge.

anolyte. During the discharge, the initial battery voltage is close to 1.50 V but decreases gradually induced by the high Ohmic overpotential of the ionic liquid anolyte that presents much higher viscosity and lower conductivity than aqueous catholyte. In fact, the higher mobility of sodium cations in the catholyte in comparison with the mobility of ions of the ionic liquid indicates that probably Na^+ acts as charge carrier through the interface during battery operation to compensate the charge.

The catholyte potential remains very stable at 0.5 V (redox potential of TEMPO) evidencing negligible overpotential. As expected, increasing the current density provokes a drop in the battery voltage, which is again triggered by the overpotential of the anolyte (see Figure 5b,c). Concerning the interface, it should be stressed that it displays an extremely flat potential close to 0 V at all current densities. In fact, the resistance at the interface represents only about 5% of the overall internal resistance of the cell during the discharge. This low contribution contrasts with the high resistances associated with ion-exchange membranes employed in conventional RFB⁴ and supposes a clear advantage of this membrane-free concept. The polarization test of the battery in Figure 5d displays a quite linear response without any evidence of kinetic losses at low current densities, denoting a quite fast electrode kinetics (see also Supporting Information Figure S8a) and a peak power density of 0.8 mW cm^{-2} , which is comparable with other reported nonaqueous ORFB.^{7,16,62}

It is important to highlight that the premature failure of the battery, driven by the sudden drop in the catholyte potential (see Figure 5a,c), results in very low value of Coulombic efficiency during the charging–discharging process ($\sim 39\%$). This is probably because of the active species depletion associated with cross-migration of hydrophobic TEMPO from the catholyte to the nonaqueous anolyte when these two immiscible phases are in contact. In fact, in this battery concept, where no membrane is used, the cross-migration or crossover of active molecules is determined by the thermodynamics of the partitioning of such species between the two liquid phases. This is quantitatively described by the partition coefficient that determines the distribution of the redox species and therefore the initial concentration of each molecule in the electrolytes. The partition coefficient of TEMPO in this system was determined by UV–vis to be 0.07. This means that once the two immiscible electrolytes are in contact, TEMPO mostly migrates toward the anolyte reaching a concentration 14 times higher than in the catholyte. This leads to a misbalance of active species in the battery, causing loss of efficiency. In fact, with the low partition coefficient of TEMPO, the charging process of battery E (apparently up to 35% of initial concentrations) can be explained only by introducing another inherent feature of this membrane-free battery: the “shuttle effect”. The “shuttle effect” is provoked by the diffusion of charged species (TEMPO^+ and $\text{pBQ}^{\bullet-}$) from the electrodes to the interphase, where they find each other undergoing spontaneous recombination via a direct electron-exchange reaction and coming back to the original species (TEMPO and pBQ), which diffuse up to the electrode, where they are oxidized/reduced again.

Here, the crossover of TEMPO through the interface was demonstrated by recording the CV of both electrolytes as prepared and after battery operation. Figure S8c shows that the CV of the anolyte after battery operation shows a redox peak at 0.6 V attributed to TEMPO molecules, which migrated from the catholyte. In addition, the CV of the catholyte after

operation (Figure S8d) displays a dramatic decrease in the peak current, becoming almost undetectable and confirming the migration of TEMPO to the anolyte.

The crossover is an important drawback also in conventional RFBs, especially in those cases in which the ion-selective membranes are substituted by cheap size-exclusion separators to reduce the resistance of the battery. In such cases, a recent strategy of using mixed-reactant electrolytes in the two battery compartments is being explored by several groups.^{57,61,63,64} Thus, although an important part of the active material is unusable, the low concentration gradient through the separator mitigates the crossover during battery operation. It is worth remarking that in this novel concept of membrane-free battery, the crossover of active species will be exclusively governed by thermodynamic aspects, such as partition coefficients. Therefore, it would be possible to completely avoid the crossover by selecting pairs of redox molecules that spontaneously migrate to opposite phases.

Battery F. In order to confirm this, TEMPO functionalized with a hydroxyl group (OH-TEMPO) in neutral media (0.5 M NaCl) was employed as the catholyte in battery F. The OH-TEMPO exhibits electrochemical performance, diffusion coefficient (D), and kinetic constant (K^0) similar to TEMPO (see Table S1), but presents some additional advantages, such as higher solubility and diminished hydrophobicity.⁵⁸ Higher solubility will allow to assemble batteries with higher concentration of active species and the reduced hydrophobicity can mitigate the cross-migration of active species through the interface. This was corroborated by the calculation of the partition coefficient of OH-TEMPO by UV–vis, which was found to be 1.02, significantly increased in comparison with the one exhibited by TEMPO in battery E (0.07). Figure S9 shows the CVs of fresh catholytes (20 mM of TEMPO and OH-TEMPO, respectively) that exhibited intense peaks for both oxidation and reduction processes. The observed changes in the CVs of the same electrolytes after battery assembly (once the two phases were formed and the thermodynamic equilibrium was reached) evidenced that TEMPO almost disappeared from catholyte in battery E because of the crossover to the anolyte, whereas an important amount of OH-TEMPO remains in the catholyte of battery F. As a result, battery F with OH-TEMPO (Figure 6c) shows a Coulombic efficiency close to 80%, which is much higher than that of battery E with non-functionalized TEMPO (less than 40%) and much better capacity retention over cycling (see Figure S8b). This result highlights the possibility of tuning the partitioning behavior of the active species by the functionalization of its structure, which brings the opportunity to develop more efficient batteries. Current research activities in our group are focused on exploiting partition coefficients as intrinsic thermodynamic tools to design high-performance membrane-free batteries.⁶⁰

It should be noted that in battery F, the anolyte was composed of 0.1 M pBQ dissolved in a mixture of PC and $\text{PYR}_{14}\text{TFSI}$ (75–25% wt). This redox electrolyte has lower viscosity and much lower cost than pure $\text{PYR}_{14}\text{TFSI}$ used in batteries A, B, and E. Moreover, the CV of this anolyte shows similar values for anodic and cathodic peak currents, demonstrating that the redox reaction of pBQ is more reversible in this electrolyte than in the electrolyte with TBAPF_6 dissolved in PC (battery D). As it is observed in Figure 6a, the individual potentials of each electrolyte during the battery operation are in good agreement with the CV

Figure 6. Performance battery F (SOC 15%). Active species concentration: 0.1 M in catholyte and anolyte. (a) Galvanostatic charge–discharge cycle at 1 mA cm⁻² for charging and 2 mA cm⁻² for discharging. (b) Polarization test during discharge. (c) Discharge voltage profiles of the battery at different current densities. (d) Cycling stability (5% SOC) at 1 mA cm⁻² for charging and 2 mA cm⁻² for discharging.

experiments (Figure 1h). Similar to the previous batteries, the anolyte showed higher overpotential than the catholyte because of different factors, such as lower conductivity and higher viscosity of the anolyte and higher diffusion limitations of pBQ in the nonaqueous anolyte (see Table S1). In addition, taking into account the different ionic mobility of the ions involved in each supporting salt, presumably, Na⁺ ions from the catholyte are those that act as charge carriers, moving through the interface to maintain the electroneutrality. It should be noted that the overpotential of the interface is very small (≈ 40 mV), with very low contribution to the internal resistance of the battery. In the discharge polarization test (Figure 6b), a peak power density of 0.9 mW cm⁻² was reached, which is 4 times higher than the power density obtained in battery D. This significant increase in the power density, associated with the higher current density reached in this battery, is probably because of the higher concentration of the electrolytes and the higher reversibility of the pBQ in battery F. In addition, increasing the current density causes a decrease in the battery voltage, as in any other type of battery, because of the higher overpotentials, as can also be observed in the polarization experiment (Figure 6c).

The cycling life of this battery was evaluated over 300 cycles, showing very stable performance (Figure 6d). The Coulombic efficiency was constant and around 75% during the whole experiment with the capacity retention (C/C_0) value of 85%. This result highlights the higher reversibility of the pBQ reaction in this anolyte (PC–PYR₁₄TFSI 75–25% wt) in comparison with the anolyte of battery D, which exhibited capacity retention lower than 60% after 14 cycles (see Figure S7d). It is important to remark that the performance of battery F is comparable with that reported in other studies based on conventional batteries with similar characteristics but using membrane.^{7,59,65} These results point out the relevance of factors such as the partition coefficients, the compatibility and affinity between the active species, and the supporting electrolyte for having a stable performance.

CONCLUSIONS

The results presented here demonstrated that our recently reported membrane-free battery concept can be applied at different pairs of immiscible electrolytes. The formulated electrolytes were based on commercially available organic redox materials, common inexpensive organic solvents, and noncorrosive aqueous media. Thus, 5 batteries were assembled with the most representative electrolytes, revealing that this membrane-free battery concept can be applied to different pairs of immiscible electrolytes containing different redox pairs. The purpose was to demonstrate at least one example of every main allure of this battery concept, which relies on the possibility of modifying either the active molecules or the electrolyte solvent giving rise to membrane-free batteries with different characteristics. As an indication of the performance of the studied batteries, changing the active species dissolved in the anolyte from pBQ to anthraquinones (examples battery A, B), a theoretical cell voltage as high as 2.1 V was achieved. This OCV is one of the highest reported and means a 50% enhancement in comparison with our previous example. In addition, a 2 times increased operating voltage (from 0.9 to 1.8 V) and 35% superior power density were attained. On the other hand, changing the solvent and the supporting electrolyte (battery D and F) reduced the battery cost, underlining the seminal importance of an adequate compatibility and affinity among redox species and supporting electrolytes. Furthermore, it has been revealed here that thermodynamic aspects, such as partition coefficients or self-discharge phenomena, are crucial factors for achieving a stable long-cycling performance in this new concept of membrane-free battery. Definitely, further improvements will be achieved by investigating deeply thermodynamic aspects to reduce the crossover contamination and working on the engineering aspects of the cell design.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

Reagents. PYR₁₄TFSI with 99.5% purity was purchased from Solvionic. PC (anhydrous 99.7% purity) and 2-butanone (ACS reagent $\geq 99.0\%$ purity) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. *p*-Benzoquinone (pBQ) ($>99.5\%$ purity) was obtained from Fluka Analytical; hydroquinone (H₂Q) reagent ($>99\%$ purity), bis-(pentylamino)anthraquinone (OilBlue N) (dye content 96%), 2,3-DMAQ (assay 98%), 2,2,6,6-tetramethyl-1-piperidinyloxy (TEMPO) (98% purity), 4-hydroxy-2,2,6,6-tetramethylpiperidine 1-oxyl (OH-TEMPO) (97% purity), and sodium chloride (ACS reagent $\geq 99.8\%$) were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich. Tetra-*n*-butylammonium hexafluorophosphate (TBAPF₆) (assay 98%) was obtained from Acros Organic. All of the reagents were used as received for electrolyte preparation.

Electrolyte Preparation. Catholytes and anolytes were prepared by dissolving organic compounds in the supporting electrolyte to obtain a solution. 2,3-DMAQ (20 mM) in PYR₁₄TFSI was used as anolyte and 20 mM of H₂Q in 0.1 M HCl as catholyte for battery A. For battery B a solution 20 mM of OilBlue N in PYR₁₄TFSI was used as anolyte and 20 mM of H₂Q in 0.1 M HCl as catholyte. For battery C, a solution 20 mM of pBQ in (0.1 M TBAPF₆) 2-butanone was used as anolyte and 20 mM of H₂Q in 0.1 M HCl as catholyte. For battery D, a 20 mM solution of pBQ in (0.1 M TBAPF₆) PC was used as anolyte and 20 mM of H₂Q (0.1 M HCl) as catholyte. For battery E, a 20 mM solution of pBQ in PYR₁₄TFSI was used as anolyte and 40 mM of TEMPO in 0.1 M NaCl as catholyte. For battery F, a 0.1 M solution of pBQ in PC + PYR₁₄TFSI (75:25% wt) was used as anolyte and a solution 0.1 M of OH-TEMPO in 0.5 M NaCl was used as catholyte.

Electrode Pretreatment. Permeable carbon felts provided by SGL CARBON GmbH (grade GFD4.6 EA) (4.6 mm thickness) were

used as electrode material in our membrane-free batteries. They were cut into squared coupons (geometric surface area $\approx 1.5 \text{ cm}^2$) pretreated by immersion in 1 M NaOH solution at 80°C during 1 h. Finally, after pH 7 was reached by washing with ultrapure water, they were dried at 100°C overnight.

Partition Coefficient Determination. The partition coefficient (K) is the ratio of concentrations of the redox compound in the two immiscible phases/electrolytes, as described by eq 1. The concentration of the redox species in each electrolyte was calculated by UV analysis.

$$K = \frac{[\text{redox molecule}]_{\text{catholyte}}}{[\text{redox molecule}]_{\text{anolyte}}} \quad (1)$$

Electrochemical Characterization. For the characterization of redox electrolytes, 3 electrode CV experiments were performed, where a glassy carbon electrode (i.d. 3 mm) was used as working electrode and a platinum mesh was utilized as counter electrode. An Ag/AgCl reference electrode was used in aqueous solutions, and for nonaqueous solutions an Ag wire was used as a pseudo-reference electrode. All electrochemical experiments were conducted using a biologic VMP multichannel potentiostat.

RDE experiments were carried out in a three-electrode cell using a glassy carbon rotating electrode (ALS Co. Ltd) of 3 mm i.d. Counter and reference electrodes were the same as those employed in the CV characterization. All the tests were conducted in a BASi RDE-3 RDE system. Linear sweep voltammetry was performed at 10 mV s^{-1} as scan rate and over a range of rotation rates from 500 to 3000 rpm. The electrolytes were purged with high-purity Ar to guarantee their deaeration. For the calculation of diffusion coefficients (D) and heterogeneous rate constant (K^0), the Koutecky–Levich equation (eq 2) was used.

$$\frac{1}{i} = \frac{1}{i_K} + \frac{1}{i_l} \quad (2)$$

where $i_K = nFAK^0C$ and $i_l = 0.62nFAD^{2/3}\omega^{1/2}\theta^{-1/6}C$, and n is the number of electrons transferred, F the Faraday constant, A the disc area, K^0 the heterogeneous rate constant, C the electroactive species concentration, D the diffusion coefficient, and θ the kinematic viscosity.

To perform the electrochemical characterization of the membrane-free batteries, polarization and galvanostatic charge experiments were carried out. First, all the batteries were galvanostatically charged to the desired SOC. To conduct galvanostatic charge–discharge experiments, the membrane-free batteries were charged to a certain SOC and then discharged at different current densities (from -0.083 to 3.5 mA cm^{-2}), with voltage cut-off of 0.5 – 0.7 V for the discharging and 2.0 V for the charging.

To obtain polarization curves, the membrane-free batteries were polarized by 1 min point-by-point galvanostatic holds from 0 to the maximum borne current density until the battery reached the safe voltage limits.

To carry out the cycle life experiments, galvanostatic charge–discharge experiments were performed continuously at 1 mA cm^{-2} for charging and 2 mA cm^{-2} for discharging, with a voltage cut-off of 1.3 and 0.2 V .

Coulombic, voltage, and energy efficiencies were calculated using eq 3–5. Coulombic efficiency (η_c) is the ratio between the charge delivered during discharge and the charge stored. Voltage efficiency (η_v) is defined as the relation between the averaged discharge voltage and the averaged charge voltage. Energy efficiency (η_e) is the multiplication of Coulombic and voltage efficiency.

$$\eta_c = \frac{Q_d}{Q_c} \quad (3)$$

$$\eta_v = \frac{V_d}{V_c} \quad (4)$$

$$\eta_e = \eta_v \eta_c \quad (5)$$

Capacity retention was calculated as the normalized discharge capacity during cycling. Thus, C_0 is the discharge capacity obtained in cycle 1. The discharge capacity obtained in each following cycle is represented as C (eq 6).

$$\text{Capacity retention} = C/C_0 \quad (6)$$

Capacity utilization (%) was calculated as the ratio between the discharge capacity and the theoretical capacity at one specific SOC. It was calculated by eq 7, where SOC refers to battery state of charge and C is the discharge capacity delivered by the battery.

$$\text{Capacity utilization (\%)} = \frac{C}{C_{t\text{-SOC}}} \times 100 \quad (7)$$

The capacity of the battery (C_t) was calculated by eq 8, where n is the amount of active species (mol), e^- is the number of electron exchanged, and F is the Faraday constant ($96\,500 \text{ s A mol}^{-1}$).

$$C_t = ne^-F \quad (8)$$

■ ASSOCIATED CONTENT

📄 Supporting Information

The Supporting Information is available free of charge on the ACS Publications website at DOI: 10.1021/acsami.8b11581.

Reaction mechanism schemes, rotating disk experiments, diffusion coefficients, rate constants, CVs of pairs of immiscible anolyte and catholyte for batteries G, H, I, and J and additional figures about the performance of batteries A, B, D, and E are supplied in the Supporting Information file (PDF)

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Notes

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